

OVERVIEW

GARCIA is concerned with the implementation of actions to promote a gender culture and combat gender stereotypes and discriminations in European Universities and research centres. By taking into account the partner organisations, but also their broader national context, this project aims to develop and maintain the research potential and skills of female and male researchers, in order to sustain the quality of their working conditions. Particular attention is given to the early stages of academic and scientific careers. The project focuses on both STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) and SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) disciplines to assure that the aim of transforming academia and research towards a more gender equal environment can be extended to all levels of the institution by putting the best systemic organisational approaches into practice. Macro, meso and micro level analyses will be followed by the implementation of action plans, which are mainly directed to: gender regimes; raising awareness about gendered practices; gender budgeting and equality in management and decision making; the leaky pipeline; implicit gendered subtexts in evaluating excellence.

University of Iceland

Gendering the Academy
and Research: combating
Career Instability and Asymmetries

Find us:

MANAGEMENT

Coordinated by:
University of Trento

The management structure has been designed in order to fit the structure of the project and to ensure that the work plan is efficiently and effectively carried out during the 36 months of the project. The main goal is to achieve a successful implementation of gender equality action plans, highly competitive scientific results and the dissemination of the outcomes in terms of policies and best practices.

Therefore, with the aim to collaborate most effectively, the management strategy promotes a flat structure, rich in communication and based on consensual decision-making, adopting a participatory approach. Responsibility for achieving the work plan for each work package has been divided among beneficiaries in accordance with their relevant expertise and scientific interests. Moreover, a crucial task of the Management Team - composed by one member of each partner institution - is to foster the participation of young researchers.

DISSEMINATION

Coordinated by:
University of Trento

GARCIA works towards the dissemination of the project outcomes and hopes to encourage other European Universities and research institutions to adopt structural change focused on gender equality. With this in mind, a series of tools and results are made available on the project website www.garciaproject.eu.

Dissemination activities are based on inputs and contributions from all partners, in line with the participative approach adopted by the project. The use of multimedia and social networks is encouraged, in order to foster the dissemination of project, activities and results and to promote communication outside the project consortium.

Communication tasks also include the organisation of a national conference in each beneficiary and a final European conference, to be held in Brussels in November 2016.

MAPPING CONTEXTS

Coordinated by:
University of Lausanne

The national environment, with its welfare, social and R&D policies, affects the way young researchers think about the idea of pursuing a career in the academy. With this in mind, the GARCIA Project aims at mapping the national context in different countries.

The project will focus on the educational, employment and family-formation patterns of women and men in the early stages of their careers, with the aim of elaborating context-sensitive action plans for equality, that take national, regional and cultural specificities into account.

The objective is to identify the practices that best support women's scientific careers in each national context, so that tailor-made recommendations for academic institutions and for policy-makers can be developed.

ORGANISATIONAL PRACTICES

Coordinated by: Scientific Research Centre
of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts

Promoting an organisational culture based on gender equality, the GARCIA project is designed with the aim to intervene both at structural and cultural level. Specifically, this work package wants to improve the daily working environment conditions in university and research institutions, by achieving the following objectives:

- to understand the career paths in the selected STEM and SSH departments, with a particular focus on female and male researchers without a permanent position, adopting both quantitative and qualitative approaches;
- to develop organisationally diversified strategies to increase the awareness of the importance of integrating a gender perspective in research and in students' curricula in academia.

In order to change the organisational gender cultures, the project is focused on identifying and improving existent practices in organisations at all the levels of the career, from the early stages (junior academic staff and temporary researchers) to the management and decision-making level.

GENDER BUDGETING

Coordinated by:
University of Iceland

The GARCIA project is interested in integrating gender perspectives in the management processes, improve gender awareness of decision makers and to promote a gender equal organisational culture.

The project addresses decision making processes in management and financing of academic institutions and the consequences they have for male and female academics. The project further focuses on recent trends such as new public management and how detrimental effects of these new trends can be counteracted.

The project will develop a gender budgeting toolkit that provides guidelines to increase transparency in decision-making, fight inequality and encourage a more stable and gender equal academic environment.

LEAKY PIPELINE

Coordinated by:
Université Catholique de Louvain

The GARCIA Project aims at mapping the Leaky Pipeline phenomenon in different contexts and institutions, in order to understand whether there are differences between STEM and SSH disciplines and to find out how and why women are more involved.

Whilst acknowledging the complexity of such process, the project focuses on three factors that play a key role in this phenomenon: the impact of productivity criteria and of mobility in "greedy institutions", which are increasingly reinforced by competitiveness; the "glass ceiling" and the "sticky floor", which are the career barriers and the difficulties preventing young researchers from accessing a stable position in scientific careers; the support in terms of career development and work-life balance that men and women receive from their institution.

In order to explore the Leaky Pipeline, PhD holders who have left universities have been interviewed. This step has a pivotal importance for the following phase, which is focused on developing a mentoring program addressed to researchers with non tenured positions.

DECONSTRUCTING EXCELLENCE

Coordinated by:
Radboud University Nijmegen

The GARCIA Project examines the formal and informal criteria that are widely used to construct scientific excellence in academia. The focus on recruitment and selection helps to unpack how the formal criteria in job descriptions and HR policies are understood and applied or transformed in committee deliberations.

The construction of academic excellence is particularly salient for those workers who have a non-tenured position, as the label of excellence is the key to their inclusion or exclusion in academia. The project aspires to increase awareness on the gendered practices and to eliminate gender inequalities in recruitment and selection processes.

The GARCIA Project will organise reflexive working groups with committee members to engage them in the construction of selection criteria that help counter gender inequalities. Also, workshops are designed to provide support to candidates who hold precarious positions and are preparing to apply for tenured positions.

ASSESSMENT & EVALUATION

Coordinated by:
Joanneum Research

Institutional progress and structural changes introduced by the GARCIA Project need to be evaluated.

The Project will conduct a self-assessment, in order to estimate outcomes and impacts of measures adopted by the participating universities and research institutions and to evaluate to what extent these measures have promoted gender equality.

The evaluation will take into account the different institutions and the different disciplines involved: SSH disciplines on the one hand and STEM fields on the other.

The WP will also provide an evaluation tool and guidelines for universities and research institutions, to enable them to monitor and assess institutional and structural changes beyond the project runtime.

GARCIA

is a European project aimed at promoting gender equality within Universities and Research Centers, by focusing on the early stages of scientific careers.

The GARCIA Project started in February 2014 and will run for 36 months.

Project coordinator

University of Trento · garciaproject@unitn.it

The GARCIA project is supported by the European Union 7th Framework Programme SiS.2013.2.1.1-1 – Grant agreement n° 611737.

Beneficiaries

University of Trento
Université catholique de Louvain
Radboud University Nijmegen
University of Iceland
University of Lausanne
Scientific Research Centre at the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts
Joanneum Research

Images©

- University of Iceland
- Université Catholique de Louvain
- University of Trento
- Scientific Research Centre at the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts
- Radboud University Nijmegen
- Joanneum Research
- University of Lausanne

Gendering the Academy and Research: combating Career Instability and Asymmetries

www.garciaproject.eu

Supported by the 7th Framework Programme of the European Union